

Experiential Photography: Awareness, Training and Personal Growth tool.

by Davide Susa ^{*1}

The photographic image is now a travel companion in a person's life, from his birth to his death, for example, the photo albums with the memories of his family, or the photo galleries that fill the memories of our mobile phones. It has always been the most emotionally powerful medium of art.

Thanks to Photography, our way of communicating has changed, there is the possibility of speaking through the image continuously (Valtorta R., 2016), from advertising, to the internet and social networks, everything is conveyed by images and their persuasive, informative or evocative power.

WHAT IS EXPERIENTIAL PHOTOGRAPHY

Judy Weiser² identifies the photographs as “...*footprints of our mind, mirrors of our lives, reflections of our hearts, suspended memories that we can hold, motionless in silence - if we wanted to, forever ... they also indicate the path that we could perhaps take, whether we already realize it or not...*”.

I make my own this sentence that fully describes the characteristics of the photographic image that expresses our present moment; our past, as we wanted to insert that scene, that person or that moment into that frame; but also our future, as in the image there are elements that concern us, which involve our perceptions and emotions, which are different from the perceptions and emotions of anyone who looks at that same image or has taken it. We choose a photograph because there are these perceptual elements that guide us and of which, often, we are not cognitively aware.

In a photo shoot we find the concepts of Subjective World and Objective World as defined below (Susa, 2020):

- ✓ **Subjective World:** allows you to express, communicate and share your perceptions, emotions, sensations, thoughts and ideas through the photographic medium;

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¹ This article is the English translation of the publication in the AIF News Magazine (October 2020) and available in Italian at the following link:

http://associazioneitalianaformatori.it/download/articoliln/2020/LN1020_Susa.pdf

² **Judy Weiser** is a psychologist, art therapist, educator, university lecturer and author, as well as one of the first pioneers of phototherapy and therapeutic photography. Founder and director of the PhotoTherapy Center in Vancouver (Canada), she is considered the world authority on the emotional significance of personal photographs.

- ✓ **Objective World:** shows the objective elements present in the photograph, the aspects that are used to create a technically good photo, that is, the technical characteristics of the image, as well as the photographic language of the author.

Experiential Photography works specifically with the Subjective World of the photographic image, and it is the peer review with the other that allows the person to open up to new points of view and new awareness. The facilitator only facilitates the training-experiential process.

The difference between Experiential Photography and Phototherapy is that phototherapy techniques are used by psychologists/psychotherapists to assist their patients who need help in resolving personal emotional problems and psychological distress. The use of photography in psychotherapy can therefore (Weiser J., 2006): help the patient build a personal organization of experiences; evoke repressed memories and facilitate an instant visual one; constitute a transitional object that connects reality; open gaps in the emotional sphere and facilitate the therapeutic relationship for two by building a bridge between therapist and patient.

The approach defined as "Experiential Photography" instead contains in an original way:

- **Photographic facilitation activities** both *active* (through the use of the camera) and *passive* (through the use of images created or chosen ad hoc by the person);
- **Experiential facilitation techniques** that offer direct experiences with reflection and facilitation tools to increase knowledge, improve skills, identify values and develop change and awareness;
- **Ludopedagogia**, an approach that uses the game as a metaphor for reality.

The training and personal growth activities based on Experiential Photography allow the person to achieve the following Goals:

- broaden one's point of view with support and comparison with the other;
- identify their values more clearly, develop greater awareness and activate the process of change;

- improve their knowledge and skills;
- develop direct experiences with reflection and facilitation tools that bring together photography, images and experiential activities.

This method of using photographic images and photography, as already mentioned is not a clinical or psychological-psychotherapeutic approach, can be usefully exploited both in the context of experiential training and personal growth, as it focuses on:

- **Exploration, in-depth analysis and elucidation on a topic/objective** - each laboratory and/or activity of Experiential Photography works on specific purposes that can range from interpersonal relationships, to communication, to business organization, etc.;
- **Creativity and development of processes in a creative way** - the photographic image allows, thanks to the association between ideas, perceptions, thoughts and emotions, to develop new awareness and concepts, also thanks to the support and comparison with other participants;
- **Communication and deeper relationships** - Experiential Photography provides a series of preliminary relational exercises that allow the establishment between the participants of a relationship of trust and deep acceptance and an authentic communication that facilitates the activities of comparison between peers where images are used.

HOW EXPERIENTIAL PHOTOGRAPHY WORKS

The photographic image is an element that serves as a facilitator of change, it manages to make the person looking at new points of view, new elements, which change the perspective with respect to perceptions and emotions triggered by the photo shoot. To activate these mechanisms we find the ideas of:

- **Figure - Background**, concept of Gestalt Psychology, where the interpretation of a photographic image, based on perceptual rules, highlights the tendency to localize an area of the photograph as a figure, and therefore closer and relevant to the background (Rubin , 1921);
- **Corrective Emotional Experience**, deepened, over 30 years ago, by Watzlawick and Nardone who took the concept from Alexander and French, extending its meaning, to the point of making it one of the cornerstones of Brief Strategic Therapy. The therapist tries to produce in the patient a "discovery effect" that allows the person to change perspective and see the observed reality transformed. This "Experience" triggers a change in the patient's way of feeling, way of perceiving reality and therefore in the actions taken to manage one's life.

The activation of the change process, the development of new awareness, develops in Experiential Photography through a work of comparison with the other (peer review). This confrontation, and therefore the underlying Corrective Emotional Experience, having an image in front of it is activated by highlighting an element that was the background for the person, and thanks to the indication of the other it becomes a figure, allowing the direct

experiences that change the perspective, facilitating new points of view, new scenarios and therefore change.

APPLICATION SCOPE OF EXPERIENTIAL PHOTOGRAPHY

The application scope of Experiential Photography is inherent in all those contexts close to personal growth, the development of new awareness and permanent training. It is an excellent approach for corporate training and the development of soft skills, and it is a method that obtains better results in group contexts, where it is possible to activate peer review situations. In individual work contexts, the Facilitator can facilitate the person by trying to postpone, in individual exercises, elements "not seen, but OBJECTIVE" from the person, activating the "Figure - Background" mechanism asking for continuous feedback with respect to the ideas proposed.

EXPERIENTIAL PHOTOGRAPHY BETWEEN METAPHORS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DEFENSES

For the Treccani Dictionary, the **Metaphor** represents the "*Expressive linguistic process ... based on an implied simile ... whereby a word or a phrase is used to express a concept different from the one they normally express*".

Photography can be understood as a metaphor for reality, it proposes and implies a personal symbolic vision of the environment around us, and compared to other metaphorical tools, such as Lego Serious Play, it contains a strong link with the world around us. Like all metaphorical tools, even Experiential Photography can activate psychological defenses in the participants in an exercise which, as Phebe Cramer³ says, unconsciously have "... *the function ... of protecting the individual from experiencing excessive anxiety*", preventing the person from being true, sincere and congruent with respect to what he thinks, feels and experiences.

To give a concrete example (see figure below), let's imagine that, during an experiential training intervention, participants were asked to identify an animal that could represent them. We have a series of photographic images of animals, a series of Lego animals and a series of colored Lego bricks. The person identifies a bear as his "representative animal" and chooses it from the metaphorical tools available to then introduce himself to the group. Surely, it will be "easier" for the person to present himself through the photographic image and with the animal representing the bear, rather than explaining to other people that the white brick represents him as a bear.

³ **Phebe Cramer** is a clinical psychologist and professor of psychology at Williams College. She is known for her research on defense mechanisms, body image and narcissism, and for her creation of a manual for coding defense mechanisms for psychological testing and personality assessment.

Immagini tratte dal libro: Serious Work (LSP)

This example highlights the main advantage of the photographic image compared to other metaphorical tools: the psychological defenses of the person will hardly be activated, as the photographic image is a representation of the reality we live and know, therefore it allows the individual to have greater availability to get involved within his comfort zone.

HOW AND WHAT KIND OF IMAGES CAN WE USE

In the activity of Experiential Photography we can use both:

- **Images previously chosen by the participant** - a selection carried out in absolute freedom and carried with them during group or individual activity. The choice is based on the theme we want to explore;
- **Images selected by the participant from a series of photos** - the facilitator makes available to participants a series of pre-defined images from which it is possible to select the one that the person feels closest to him or her and to the theme to explore. These series of photos can be built by the Facilitator or purchased with ready-made sets available on the market, often also organized by theme to be explored (eg relationships, objectives, etc.). Among those I use most in the field of Experiential Photography activities and workshops, both for the richness and the quality of the images, I can suggest those of the producer Metafox⁴.

Our excursus highlighted how photographic image and Experiential Photography can be a tool to have available in the toolbox for today's trainers.

⁴ **Metafox** is a German company made up of a team of trainers who develop tools for the world of education, mainly sets of photographic images. The tools can be purchased on Amazon, an example: <https://amzn.to/2YAVOvD>